
Job and Career Satisfaction of Staff Nurses in Secondary Government Hospital: Basis for a Retention Program

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ABSTRACT

The study aimed to assess the job and career satisfaction and performance of nurses at President Ramon Magsaysay Memorial Hospital (PRMMH) during the fiscal year 2018. A locally constructed questionnaire was used as the primary data gathering instrument of the study and was given to fifty (50) nurse-respondents of PRMMH in Iba, Zambales. The tabulated data in Microsoft Excel 2016 were treated using Statistical Package for Social Sciences Version 20 (SPSS v.20) software. Majority of the respondents at President Ramon Magsaysay Memorial Hospital are females, single, have a bachelor's degree, is in Nurse I position, are ward nurses, are in contractual employment status, salary ranges from P10,000 to P12,000 and renders care in the hospital for a year. Almost all of the respondents underwent trainings and seminars in different areas. Nurses in terms of compensation and benefits, work relationships, work environment and career enhancement are satisfied. The influence of compensation and benefits, organizational policies, work relationship, and career enhancement are no significant, only the work environment appeared significant in this study. It is recommended that PRMMH should hire additional staff nurses have a safe nurse-patient ratio. Reward system must be developed to encourage performance of staff nurses which eventually elevate performance standard. The administrator should continue to send their nurses, not only those in the higher positions into trainings and seminars that plays a vital role in the improvement of quality care. There should also be a standard number of years rendered as to when a contractual employee becomes a regular employee.

Keywords: Statistical Package for Social Sciences, Contractual employee, Iba, Zambales, Safe nurse-patient ratio

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INTRODUCTION

The exodus of nurses to the high paying jobs abroad has recently been described as a “national hemorrhage”, a rather shrill cry if only because the phenomenon is nothing new. If one considers that the Philippines has been exporting doctors and nurses abroad since the 1960s, then doomsday scenarios of the country's hospitals and clinics being packed with patients but emptied of doctors and nurses in the near future are just that doomsday scenarios created by prophets of doom. There's really no need to sound the alarm anew because the alarm has been ringing all along.

The Philippines in now left with only nine hundred sixty (960) privately run hospitals and four hundred seventy-six (476) government hospitals according to the latest statistics from the Department of Health.

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Dela Pena (2023) reported that as many as 1,000 hospitals have closed down since 2000 due to the steady departure of nurses seeking higher pay abroad. Nevertheless, Orte et al., (2020) mentioned that even level 1 hospitals in public and private still provide appropriate quality care to patients. The span of year 2000 saw the progressive development of President Ramon Magsaysay Memorial Hospital (PRMMH) in its physical environment due to the inflow of assistance coming from Japan International Cooperating Agency (JICA) and from the national government. New construction of buildings was completed, renovation was undertaken and its grounds and pathways were improved. The hospital became one of the priorities of the provincial government, thus it was upgraded comparable to the best in the region. Purchase of equipment and facilities were manifested like X-ray machines and CT scan. Continuous staff training of doctors was implemented together with the additional hiring of nursing service personnel.

However, despite all these good turns of events that took place at the PRMMH, still the hospital experiences decrease in the number of nurses. In a five-year period from 2011 to 2016, there was a decrease of 30 nursing personnel, majority of them (23) went abroad for better employment and security, while the rest was caused by natural causes like retirement (5) and death (2). Decrease number of nurses means turnover of function. Without proper replacement of man power in the health care delivery system, tends to create disruption and hindrance to hospital effectiveness in rendering health care services in mankind.

Extension of hours of duty will be expected if there is not enough manpower. Oftentimes, nurses work load increases. Bautista et al., (2019) claimed that workload is the most frequent stressor of nurses. They go beyond eight hours of duty in a day which may lead to unfavorable burnout that affects their performance and quality care. Consequently, this led to over fatigue and stress (Asio & Garcia, 2023) affecting the health condition of a personnel, leading to absenteeism which in turn may also pose difficulty for the remaining staff to operate decisively and efficiently. Often times, work flow is disrupted, relevant and important decisions were affected. Absenteeism can result in a drastic reduction in quality of output, and in some cases, it can bring about direct impact on the hospital effectiveness and efficiency and if not be attended promptly, lead to a closure.

Job and career satisfaction is part of life satisfaction. Asio (2021a) mentioned that a link exists between working environment and organizational satisfaction. Sapar and Oducado (2021) also claimed that nurses in the Philippines were neither satisfied nor dissatisfied with their job. In terms of career satisfaction, Oducado (2020) mentioned that Filipino nurses were satisfied with their careers. The nature of one's environment in the job influences one's feeling on the job. Similarly, it is an important part of life as it influences one's general life satisfaction. Ancheta et al., (2021) also proved that nurses' job satisfaction is above average. Also, Bautista et al., (2023) claimed that nurses have high work engagement. Thus, employee engagement is important and should be considered accordingly (Mondejar & Asio, 2023). Someday, each one of us may have the chance to handle people in various capacities, as supervisor, manager, and department head, principal or probably an employer, understanding the complexities of what really satisfies one in a particular job of great essence. If you do a good job, you intrinsically feel good about it. Asio (2021b) also mentioned that department predicts work productivity among employees. Additionally, assuming that the organization rewards productivity, higher productivity increases verbal recognition, pay level, and probabilities for promotion. These rewards, in turn, increases level of satisfaction with the job.

According to Aasami et al., (2015), it is an emotional response to one's task as well as the physical and social conditions of the work place. In concept, job and career satisfaction also indicates the degree to which the expectations in someone's psychological contract are fulfilled. Asio (2020) once mentioned that employees' performance review can determine the organizational climate of the workplace. Cornito and Cunanan (2019) also found that nurses are undecided in their turnover intention and job satisfaction is correlated turnover intention.

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Meanwhile, a person actually should enjoy his work, should get from it an actual pleasure. Factors, which contribute to make teaching a pleasure, will act as a powerful motivation for satisfaction which the administrator should strive to provide nurses. Asio and Riego de Dios (2021) once shared that age and civil status were factors for employees to procrastinate at work. The wise administrator sparks in nurses concern for progress through creative activity. Mondejar and Asio (2022) stated that employees can be satisfied with their supervisors if appropriate human resource management is practiced. This context may be attained when there is an atmosphere of freedom so that nurses are to function up with pleasure to their capacity. It will make the nurses' tasks interesting and inspiring.

Health providers play a major role in the existence of hospitals. Without them, the health of the populace will be at risk. Nurses are considered as the heart of healthcare system, and if they are not satisfied, it's going to have repercussions down the lines on quality of care. Hence, employees' satisfaction affects every aspect of practice, from patient satisfaction to overall productivity. This idea is true since Asio and Jimenez (2020) found out a favorable job satisfaction among employees in their article.

Considering all the medical efforts exerted by the hospital staff in promoting the health concern of the populace, it is high time as a matter of management control to receive feedbacks from its subordinates regarding their satisfaction on their job. In event of significant deviations of actual results, management can reinforce whatever weaknesses observed in program planning and implementation. It is along this concern that the researcher is moved to conduct this study.

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

This study utilized the descriptive-survey type of research. Asio (2021c) mentioned that in this design, the researcher determines if an intervention impacts an outcome. It involves the elements or interpretation of the meaning of the significance of what is described. The descriptive method was preferred because the main concern of the study is to analyze the factors influencing the job and career satisfaction of nurses at President Ramon Magsaysay Memorial Hospital (PRMMH). Further, the research method yields valid results to a manageable number and can be accomplished with limited resources and time. The researcher also made use of the survey technique through the survey instrument to obtain data from the respondents.

Respondents

The study utilized a purposive sampling which consists of fifty (50) nurses coming from different areas or ward assignment of PRMMH. The respondents of the study consist of Nurse I with 41 respondents, Nurse II with 6 respondents, and Nurse III with 3 respondents.

Research Instrument

A locally constructed questionnaire was used as the primary data gathering instrument of the study. The questionnaire was consisted of two parts. Part I includes the profile of the nurses. Part II includes the factors that contributes to job and career satisfaction. The Four Point Likert Scale was used to determine the job and career satisfaction of nurses in the President Ramon Magsaysay Memorial Hospital. It consisted of 10 items per indicators and an additional 5 with a total of 55 items for Part II. The first draft of the questionnaire was constructed in close coordination with the researcher's adviser and critic. After all the needed corrections by them, were done the refined questionnaire was then submitted to the competent persons for further correction and inputs and for construct validation. Their comments and recommendations were considered before finalizing the instruments. Upon completion of the questionnaire,

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it was field-tested to non-respondents of the study before it was administered to the respondents of PRMMH.

Statistical Treatment of data

The tabulated data in Microsoft Excel 2016 were treated using Statistical Package for Social Sciences Version 20 (SPSS v.20) software. Manual calculations were disregarded; thus, presentation of formula is not necessary.

The following are the statistical treatment used in this study:

Frequency and Percentage Distribution was used to categorize the profile of the respondents. Particularly their sex, civil status, highest educational qualification, length of service, position, current area/ward assignment, type of employment, salary range, relevant trainings and number of seminars attended. Weighted Mean was used to describe the respondents' level of job and career satisfaction of nurse-respondents in terms of: Compensation and Benefits, Organizational Policies, Work Relationships, Work Environment and Career Enhancement. The 4-point Likert scale below was used for the descriptive ratings of the calculated weighted means. Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) and T Test were used check if there a significant difference in the job and career satisfaction of the respondents when grouped according to profile variables. Moreover, Post Hoc Test using Tukey HSD was run to identify which variable differs among the rest in case of significance in the ANOVA (F Test). The Level of Significance is 0.05. Multiple Regression was used check if job and career satisfactions significantly affect the performances of the nurses-respondents.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This section tackles the results of the gathered data. It significantly includes relevant aspects leading to the analysis of the findings particularly on the profile of the respondents in terms of gender, marital status, length of service, relevant trainings and job position; level of job satisfaction of nurses in terms of compensation and benefits, organizational policies, work relationship, work environment, career enhancement and performance.

The results highlight that significant difference of work environment with job and career satisfaction. Moreover, Compensation and benefits, organizational policies, work relationship and work environment have no significant relationship with job and career satisfaction.

Profile Variables

Sex. There is an imbalance between the number of male and female respondents. There were thirty-two (32) female nurses or sixty-four (64%) percent and there were eighteen (18) male nurses or thirty-six (36%) percent, a total of fifty respondents. There are more female respondents than male respondents. According to the most recent NMC figures (2017), only one in ten nurses on the register were male, a figure that has remained static for the past four years. Although there has been a rise in men entering the profession in the last few decades, it has been a small, slow one. While perceptions are beginning to change, some nurses believe that the profession is still seen as a feminine one.

Civil Status. There were twenty-eight (28) or fifty-six (56%) single nurses, fifteen (15) or thirty (30%) percent were married, two (2) or four (4%) percent were legally separated, and five (5) or ten (10%) percent are widower. In majority, the nurses in PRMMH are single. Upon interview, nurses opt not to get married because according to them, marriage is not given priority nowadays and may cost a fortune on preparing

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for such event. Some of these nurses are newbies and chose to remain single in order to spend more time in their nursing profession.

Highest Educational Attainment. There is one (1) nurse or two (2%) percent with Doctoral Degree, nine (9) or eighteen (18%) percent with Masters' Degree, and forty (40) or eighty (80%) percent with Bachelors' Degree. As yielded by the data, most nurses have Bachelors' degree. Most them are advance beginners in the field of nursing, they are still exploring the world of clinical nursing and how they will manage their time when it comes to their career and social life. Entering post graduate studies is still not in their top priorities.

Length of Service. There were twenty-nine or fifty-eight (58%) percent of nurses who are 1-5 years in service, thirteen (13) or twenty-six (26%) percent who are 6-10 years in service, two (2) or four (4%) percent who are 11-15 and 15-20 years in service, and four or eight (8%) percent who has rendered 21 and above in nursing service. It was found out that most of the respondents rendered service in the hospital for one year. It is worth mentioning, that based on the obtained data, the nurse respondents are advanced beginners. According to Patricia Benner's Stages of Clinical Competence, advance beginners are those newly grads in their first jobs; nurses have had more experiences that enable them to recognize recurrent, meaningful components of a situation. They have the knowledge and the know-how but not enough in-depth experience. These nurses are what we call "newbies" in their jobs.

Position. There were forty-one (41) or eighty-two (82%) who are in Nurse I, six (6) or twelve (12%) are in Nurse II or Head Nurses and three (3) or six (6%) are in Nurse III or Supervisors, whose job is to govern their assigned area or ward. Generally, the Nurse 1 respondents are greater in number than those in the supervisory level because most of the respondents are advance beginners and does not qualify to be in a higher position.

Area of Duty. There were thirty-six (36) or seventy-two (72%) percent respondents who are assigned to ward, five (5) or ten (10%) percent in Emergency Room, four (4) or eight (8) percent in Intensive Care Unit, two (2) or four (4%) percent in Operating Room, and three (3) or six (6%) percent in Delivery Room. As yielded by the data, most of the respondents came from ward. There is a total of eight (8) wards in PRMMH and they outnumber the special clinical areas.

Employment Status. Five (5) or ten (10%) percent of the respondents are in Regular *plantilla* position, fourteen (14) or twenty-eight (28%) percent are permanent casual, thirty-one or sixty-two (62%) percent are in the contract of service. In majority, are in contract of service. Upon entry to President Ramon Magsaysay Memorial Hospital, employment status will be automatically be in the contract of service. This started in 2016, where volunteers and job offer positions for Nurses were no longer allowed by the office of the Governor. Regular *plantilla* and casual positions are to be decided by the government office and it depends on the number of years rendered in the hospital, the educational background and clinical skills of the Nurse. In the study of Lorenzo et al., (2021), most of their respondents were regular in status which contradicts the current result of the study.

Salary Bracket. most of the respondents has a salary bracket of 12,000-13,999. They are the ones under the contract of service. Casual employees have a salary bracket of 14,000-15,999 and regular employees has a salary bracket of 16,000 and above. Regular employees have more benefits than the two mentioned employment status. Only one of the respondents is receiving a salary of 10,000, and is subject to increase to 12,000 upon approval of the government office.

Trainings. The study yielded fifteen (15) or thirty (30%) percent of the respondents having BLS, ACLS and IVT trainings. Intravenous therapy training had been a pre-requisite for staff nurses beginning employment but was later on reiterated by Department of Health Undersecretary Roger Tong-An last October 16, 2016 that renewal and training is not needed. Since RA 9173 became a law, the requirement of RA 7164 (the Philippine Nursing act of 1991) to have "special training" for the administration of

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intravenous medications, has been completely removed. Under the Philippine Nursing Act of 2002, the administration of parenteral medications no longer needs any additional training as per Section 28, The Scope of Nursing. Despite these changes, still, four (4) of the respondents or eight (8%) percent underwent IVT training on 2017 in order to improve their intravenous insertion skills.

Nine (9) or eighteen (18%) percent of respondents had BLS training and five (5) or ten (10%) percent had BLS-ACLS training. BLS outnumbered BLS-ACLS primarily because of the cost of training; the latter is more expensive. Seventeen (17) or thirty-four (34%) percent, which accounts for the highest number of respondents, had BLS and IVT because these two trainings are easily accessible for the respondents. It is catered by the hospital and by the Red Cross-Iba Chapter, which is quiet near PRMMH.

Seminars. There are three seminar locations in total: institutional, local and regional. Institutional seminars are those that take place in President Ramon Magsaysay Memorial Hospital. In majority, institutional seminars has the greatest number of attendees from the respondents and regional seminars has the least number of respondents. If the seminar is being conducted in the workplace, it is more accessible by the nurses unlike if it is in local or regional, there will be an additional cost for transportation and will be more costly for the nurses.

Level of Job and Career Satisfaction of Nurse- Respondents

Compensation and Benefits. The respondents were satisfied as shown by the overall weighted mean of 2.51. Compensation is one of the important factors that affect the satisfaction of the employees. If an employee feels that the salary given to him is not enough that is the time that he will change his amount of duty based on the salary he received. Benefits are considered an “extra” aside for having monthly salary. Benefits are non-financial form of compensation that serves as an addition to enrich the employees’ lives. Some of the respondents already spent years working in the hospital and are already receiving a salary that is enough to sustain a living. Additionally, majority of the respondents are single and upon interview, some of them are satisfied with their salary because they have no children to feed.

Organizational Policies. The respondents were moderately satisfied as shown by the overall weighted mean of 2.46. The ideal nurse to patient ratio, according to the Philippines Department of Health, is 1:12, but this is hardly true in many hospitals. In PRMMH, Pediatric Ward has the greatest number of patients and nurse-patient ratio sometimes escalates up to 2:70. Another thing is the sanitation and proper waste disposal. Maintaining the cleanliness of the hospital is quite difficult due to lack of manpower. There are waste bins for proper waste disposal in every area of PRMMH, however, proper placement of trashes is not clearly implemented.

Work Relationship. The respondents were satisfied as shown by the overall weighted mean of 2.60. President Ramon Magsaysay Memorial Hospital always maintains the image of being professional inside the workplace. Before starting to work in PRMMH, orientation to new nurses is conducted in order for them to know who the Heads of the hospital are and to familiarize them with the policies. It is also strictly implemented to give respect to the seniors.

Work Environment. The respondents were satisfied as shown by the overall weighted mean of 2.69. However, because PRMMH is a public hospital and caters a lot of patients every day, equipment and paraphernalia that are available in each area are not enough to be used for the patients. Nurses are left with no choice but to improvise. Instead of using a pressure infuser bag for blood transfusions, a blood pressure cuff is always used. In the paper of Asio (2021d), he mentioned that respondents had a general agreement on the working environment that they have.

Career Enhancement. The respondents were satisfied as shown by the overall weighted mean of 2.86. Organizations that empower management of career are more likely to enlarge employee’s satisfaction of job (Modise 2023). As previously mentioned, PRMMH maintains an image of professionalism inside the

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workplace. But upon interview, some nurses see this “professionalism” as being strict and controlling, making it a barrier in building self confidence among staff; thus, receiving the only moderately satisfied rating among the ten.

CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

In the light of the foregoing findings, the following conclusions are hereby forwarded.

1. That the nurses working in President Ramon Magsaysay Memorial Hospital are mostly females, single and had attended trainings and seminars.
2. Nurses in terms of compensation and benefits, work relationships, work environment and career enhancement are satisfied.
3. The influence of compensation and benefits, organizational policies, work relationship, and career enhancement are no significant, only the work environment appeared significant in this study.

Based on the foregoing findings and conclusions, the following recommendations are hereby presented:

1. President Ramon Magsaysay Memorial Hospital should hire additional male nurses in cases of transport and turning of heavy patients. Highly qualified nurses should be hired in order to have a safe nurse-patient ratio.
2. Reward system must be developed to encourage performance of staff nurses which eventually elevate performance standard.
3. The administrator should continue to send their nurses, not only those in the higher positions into trainings and seminars that plays a vital role in the improvement of quality care.
4. There should be a standard number of years rendered as to when a contractual employee becomes a regular employee.
5. That this can be replicated, provided however, that other indicators should be incorporated, such as comparative study between the job and career satisfaction, productivity of nurses as influenced by the managerial skills of both private and public hospitals vis-à-vis performance level of the different medical departments.

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